

Sustainable Cultivation of Vannamei Shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) Using Innovative Feed Additives

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Abstract

The study focuses on the sustainable cultivation of *Litopenaeus vannamei* shrimp in Navsari district, Gujarat, India, utilising innovative feed additives from Intron Life Sciences that primarily include probiotics, for gut & pond management, Tribiotic, Phytobiotics, Minerals and growth promoters. A comprehensive pond preparation and management approach over a 161-day culture period in 16 ponds resulted in a utilisation and survival rate of 78.85%, with individual pond survival rates ranging from 65.95% to 88.29%. *Vibrio* colony counts are within standard limits, with green colonies below 50 and yellow-coloured colonies below 500 throughout the culture period. A feed conversion ratio of 1.59 indicates a better feed utilisation. The results demonstrate the benefits of eco-friendly, organic feed additives for a healthier shrimp with sustainable aquaculture practices.

Keywords: *Litopenaeus vannamei*, sustainable aquaculture, feed additives, probiotics, *Vibrio*, Intron Life Sciences.

Suggested citation: Pradipkumar, V., Krishna, B., & Kumar, V.P. (2025). Sustainable Cultivation of Vannamei Shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) Using Innovative Feed Additives. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(6), 208-216. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(6).19

Introduction

The aquaculture industry plays a significant role in meeting the global seafood demand. Shrimp cultivation, primarily using *Litopenaeus vannamei* (*L. vannamei*), is reducing demand due to its faster growth cycle, disease resistance, and high market value (Verdegem *et al.*, 2023). India is the world's second-largest producer of shrimp, with farming done in Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, Gujarat, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, and Goa (Salunke *et al.*, 2020).

Within India, Gujarat is the fourth most significant and productive state for shrimp production (Nisar *et al.*, 2021), with Valsad, Navsari, Surat, and Bharuch districts contributing 95% of the state's output, with land available of 89340.91 hectare and allotted of 8119.18 hectares producing 54,792 & 54,418 metric tons for year 2022-23, 2023-24 respectively (Fisheries Statistics of Gujarat State, 2022-23 & 2023-24).

Significant losses in *L. vannamei* culture are due to diseases such as White Spot Syndrome Virus (WSSV), White Faecal Syndrome (WFS), Black Gill Disease (BGD), Loose Shell Syndrome (LSS), Running Mortality Syndrome (RMS), and Enterocytozoon Hepatopenaei (EHP) (Venkateswarlu and Venkatrayulu, 2019). *Vibrio* species are predominant pathogens that cause various diseases and significant

economic losses in aquaculture. *V. harveyi*, *V. anguillarum*, *V. parahaemolyticus*, and *V. vulnificus* are mainly associated with mortalities in hatcheries and grow-out ponds (Shanmugasundaram *et al.*, 2015). EHP, *V. parahaemolyticus*, and WSSV infections often occur individually or as co-infections (Babu *et al.*, 2021).

Earlier, conventional shrimp farming practices were often dependent primarily on the indiscriminate use of antibiotics, resulting in antimicrobial resistance, potential health risks for consumers, environmental degradation, and the use of chemicals (Vignesh *et al.*, 2011; Salunke *et al.*, 2020). The use of antibiotics in aquaculture is a global concern that impacts the Indian export sector, as it faces rejection due to the detection of antibiotic residues (Parvez & Vijaya, 2020). Gram-negative bacteria exhibited relatively higher drug resistance, and the excessive use of antibiotics in shrimp farming may disseminate multidrug resistance to other heterotrophic bacterial populations through horizontal gene transfer (Nadella, *et al.*, 2021). The highest resistance was observed towards oxytetracycline, followed by erythromycin, cotrimoxazole, ciprofloxacin, and chloramphenicol. Bacteria isolated from shrimp samples showed higher resistance to the tested antibiotics compared to those from sediment and water samples (Ranjit *et al.*, 2021). Cultured shrimps can serve as vehicles for *Vibrio* resistant to β -lactam and tetracycline (Albuquerque Costa *et al.*, 2015). Every recovered isolate of *Vibrio* was resistant to tetracycline and ampicillin (Prabina *et al.*, 2023). Antimicrobial resistance was frequently detected for most of the isolated *V. harveyi*, which were highly susceptible to ampicillin, cefaclor, ciprofloxacin, penicillin, rifampicin, and vancomycin (Stalin and Srinivasan, 2016). *V. parahaemolyticus*, a common pathogen, resisted erythromycin and nalidixic acid (Babu *et al.*, 2021). These alarming observations are a primary concern regarding the entry of AMR genes into the food chain, and most countries, including India, have banned the use of antibiotics.

Consequently, sustainable aquaculture practices that focus on enhancing natural immunity, preventing disease, and promoting eco-friendly pond management are gaining importance.

Shrimp farming environments are complex ecosystems with numerous interacting challenges. These include seed quality, stocking density, water quality, soil health, pond bottom conditions, accumulation of toxic gases, environmental fluctuations, feed quality, feed and animal waste management, mortality, organic matter dynamics, plankton balance, mineral absorption, osmoregulation, gut health, and pathogen control (including *Vibrio*, WSSV, white gut, and white muscle disease). The other challenges include managing biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), water hardness, pH, and dissolved oxygen, as well as ensuring adequate manpower skills (Tandel and Maheta, 2018; Nisar *et al.*, 2021).

Probiotics, prebiotics, postbiotics, minerals, vitamins, enzymes, immunostimulants, etc., are now widely used feed additives in shrimp farming to stimulate immunity, improve feed digestion, and enhance water quality (Thornber *et al.*, 2020; Li *et al.*, 2024; Nolasco-Alzaga *et al.*, 2025).

Intron Life Sciences Private Limited, through intensive research and development, world-class manufacturing, certified facilities, proprietary strains, biologically activated minerals, lyophilised technology, its "Naturelle" concept for phytobiotics, Probiotics, Prebiotics and Postbiotics containing BIOFENCE AQUA (World's First Tribiotic) and species-specific formulations, offers synergistic solutions to prevent and address these challenges through a holistic management approach which commands better market value for farmers.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in the selected ponds of Navsari district, Gujarat, India, across 16 ponds that stretch across 9.92 acres, and was monitored over a period of 5 months from April to September 2023. Additionally, one sedimentation pond (1 acre) and one reservoir pond (5 acres) were included. The cultivation employed innovative Intron products (Table 1). Six 10 HP motor pumps were used to lift

water from the reservoir pond to the feeder channel. Each pond had two inlet pipes (6-inch diameter) to fill with water. All culture ponds, 2 meters deep with clay-type soil, maintained a water level of 1.5 – 1.6 meters.

Pond Preparation

The pond bottom preparation involved two weeks of drying and removing the upper layer. The pond bottom pH was maintained at a normal level of approximately 7.8. The ponds were filled with water from creeks. After pumping, bleaching powder is applied at a dosage of 300kg/Ha (30 PPM). This was followed by water treatment using a fermented liquid (30kg of rice bran, 1kg of jaggery, and 250ml of INTRAFERM). The first dose was applied four days before stocking, followed by four additional doses after stocking to establish a plankton bloom.

Seed Stocking

Shrimp post larvae (PL 09) were procured from a commercial hatchery. Post-larvae were packed in oxygenated polybags and checked for the White Spot Syndrome Virus (WSSV), with results confirming the absence of the virus. On-farm acclimation included adequate aeration and adjustment of salinity to 20 ppt. Seed bags were floated in pond water to adjust the temperature, and pond water was gradually added to regulate salinity and pH before the seeds were slowly released into the ponds.

Feeding

Crumble feed was administered up to 25 days, followed by pellet feed. Feed was given four times daily until harvest. The survival percentage was calculated at the end of the crop.

Water Quality Monitoring

Throughout the culture period, water quality parameters, including dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, temperature, and salinity, were monitored daily using a DO meter, pH meter, thermometer, and refractometer, respectively. Ammonia, nitrite, and nitrate levels were measured using an API kit, ensuring optimal conditions for *L. vannamei* shrimp.

Vibrio Testing

Vibrio levels were monitored using a Thiosulfate-Citrate-Bile Salt-Sucrose (TCBS) agar medium. *Vibrio* (green and yellow colonies) were first tested three weeks after stocking, followed by two-week intervals, and subsequently monitored weekly.

Water was added as required to maintain the water level. Paddlewheel aerators provided aeration, with 8 HP and 12 HP units deployed depending on the pond size. Intron aquaculture products were applied to feed or directly into ponds, as detailed in Table 1, to enhance water quality and control *Vibrio*.

Check trays were maintained from 30 to 120 days of culture (DOC). After 30 DOC, cast net sampling was performed at 7-day intervals to monitor shrimp growth and health. Parameters were assessed as per the methodology outlined by Kotiya and Vadher (2021). During harvest, all water from the culture ponds was drained into the sedimentation pond and released into the open creek.

Table 1. Intron Life Sciences Products with dosage and application

Product	Type	Pond Preparation	Regular use (dosage)	Application
ALBATREAT	Phytoalkaloids for natural immunity booster against white gut and white faecal diseases		10ml/kg of feed	As required

AMMOX-L	Probiotics for ammonia management		1L/Ha	As required
BACTOPIOUS	Probiotics for pond management		1 vial/acre	As required
BIOFENCE AQUA	Probiotics, Prebiotics & Post biotics acting as shrimps natural shield		5g/kg	Weekly 4 times
BIOMOULT	Minerals inducing stress free moulting naturally		10g/kg	Lunar days
INTRACEE	Stable and highly bioavailable Vitamin C		2g/kg	4 times/week
INTRAFERM	Liquid yeast for immunity and pond management	Fermenting along with Rice bran and Jaggery	250ml	
INTRAMIN-O	Biologically activated highly bioavailable minerals	10kg/Ha – depending on the bloom	10% of daily feed	Every 10 days – Pond application
INTRAMIN-OL	Biologically activated highly bioavailable minerals in liquid form		10ml/kg of feed	Loose shell & growth issues
INTRASHIELD	Phytoalkaloids for potent immunity and performance booster		10ml/kg of feed	Weekly 3 times
MAAVERIC-PS	Stabilized PS bacteria for pond management		15% of daily feed	Every 15 days – pond application
REALBIND	Unique feed binder with essential qualities		20ml/kg of feed	Regular use
OXYWIND	For DO		Depending on Pond condition	As required
SOILEX	Soil Probiotics	3kg/Hectare	2% of total feed	Every 15 days up to 45 days – pond application
TOTAL	Probiotics for Water and soil management		1% of total feed	Every 15 days up to 45 days and every week after 45 days – Pond Application
SUMO	Growth promoter		10g/kg of feed	4 days/week

Data Collection and Analysis

The following parameters are monitored:

- Survival rate
- Feed conversion ratio (FCR)
- *Vibrio* (green and yellow) colony counts

Results

This study evaluated the performance of Vannamei shrimp farming using innovative Intron feed additives. Sixteen ponds, totalling 9.92 acres, were stocked with 28,13,000 shrimp on April 19, 2023. The 161-day old culture (DOC) concluded with the final harvest on September 27, 2023. Harvesting occurred in two phases: the first at an average of 109 DOC (average count of 39 shrimp/kg) and the second/final harvest at an average of 153 DOC (average count of 30.33 shrimp/kg).

22,18,147 shrimp were harvested, representing a 78.85% harvest efficiency. This yielded a total harvested biomass of 66,339 kg, with an average productivity of 2,358 kg per 100,000 stocked shrimp. The overall average survival rate across all ponds was 78.85%, with individual pond survival ranging from 65.95% to 88.29%, with better sustainable practices. Total feed consumption was 1,05,513 kg, with an average feed conversion ratio (FCR) of 1.59, with individual pond FCRs ranging from 1.33 to 1.95. All the water parameters are within the range.

Individual pond performance provided valuable insights. Pond 16 has the highest survival rate (88.29%) with a better FCR of 1.42, demonstrating effective pond management and feed utilisation. On the contrary, Pond 9 has the lowest survival rate (68.94%) and the highest FCR of 1.95 (Table 2 - Appendix).

Vibrio colony counts were analysed for green (Figure 1) and yellow colonies (Figure 2). Green *Vibrio* colony counts consistently remained below the standard limit of <50 across all ponds and sampling dates, with average counts ranging from 1.88 to 32.5 colonies. The highest counts were observed in June and July, particularly in Ponds 3, 4, and 8, suggesting a possible seasonal influence or localised management issues. However, counts returned to acceptable levels (<50) in subsequent months.

Figure 1. Trends of Green Color *Vibrio* Colonies

Yellow *Vibrio* colony counts remained below the threshold of <500 colonies, ranging from 84.37 to 306.87. The highest levels were reported in May, June, and July, especially in ponds 8, 9, and 10, and declined in August and September.

Figure 2. Trends of Yellow Color *Vibrio* colonies

Discussion

Pond management, achieved through continuous monitoring of water quality and shrimp health are the primary factors in achieving positive outcomes. Reducing *Vibrio* populations is important in preventing disease outbreaks.

Veterinary medicinal products have a positive impact on stocking density, survival rate, and production. Using higher quantities of environmental modifiers and probiotics suggests an awareness of their utility in maintaining optimal water and soil parameters, improving pond health, and reducing stress and disease episodes (Patil *et al.*, 2022). Probiotic bacteria cells and cell-free extract encourage an eco-friendly approach to treatments, controlling or preventing pathogen infection (Babu *et al.*, 2021).

Probiotics in aquaculture enhance feed conversion efficiency and disease resistance by modifying gut microbial activity, while water probiotics improve environmental quality by reducing the production of toxic metabolites (Zhang, *et al.*, 2024). Gut probiotics, water probiotics, and soil probiotics are commonly used in Indian aquaculture to improve disease resistance and digestibility and to mitigate toxic nitrogenous and sulphur metabolites (Verschuere, Rombaut, Sorgeloos, & Verstraete, 2000; Mohapatra, Chakraborty, Kumar, DeBoeck, & Mohanta, 2013; Banerjee & Ray, 2017; Hasan & Banerjee, 2020). Recent reviews highlight various mechanisms of gut probiotics, including competition, inhibitory metabolites, environmental modification, immunomodulation, and stress relief (Zorriehzahra, Delshad, & Adel, 2016; Dawood, Koshio, Abdel-Daim, & Van Doan, 2019), as well as their role in disease resistance (Hoseinifar, Sun, Wang, & Zhou, 2018), symbiotic formulations (Hai, 2015), and host-specific benefits (Van, Hoseinifar, Ringø, *et al.*, 2020).

Phytobiotics enhance gut health, performance, survival rates, feeding rate and FCR (Kesselring *et al.*, 2021). Phytobiotics significantly enhanced the growth and survival of Pacific white shrimp following a challenge with *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* (Ma *et al.*, 2024).

Our results are similar to those of Servin *et al.*, 2021, who had positive production outcomes when supplementing functional feed additives in shrimp feed under practical farming conditions. The results demonstrate the potential of sustainable aquaculture practices in *L. vannamei* cultivation. The 78.85% survival rate and 1.59 FCR indicate effective pond management and efficient feed utilisation. Intron feed additives, including proprietary probiotics, have positively influenced shrimp health, survival rate, FCR, and pond conditions. Farmers can achieve better production outcomes by adopting sustainable practices and minimising environmental impact.

Conclusion

This study emphasises the role of feed additives in promoting sustainable aquaculture practices, particularly in transforming shrimp farming with better yields, improved FCR, reduced *Vibrio* count and supported sustainability, which helps in quality shrimp. The inclusion of Intron's innovative feed additives, along with proprietary strains and scientifically based formulations, technology-driven, and time-tested in the routine process, enables shrimp farmers to achieve consistent production and improved crop quality through sustainable and environmentally friendly cultivation.

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Appendix

Table 2. Summary of Stocking, Harvest Details, Survival Rate, Total Biomass, Feed Usage, and FCR for Vannamei Shrimp Trials across 16 Ponds in Navsari, Gujarat

STOCKING DETAILS				1ST PARTIAL HARVEST					FINAL HARVEST					TOTAL SUMMARY					
POND	AREA (ACRES)	STOCKED	DATE	DATE	DOC	WT. (kg)	CT.	PCS	DATE	DOC	WT. (kg)	CT.	PCS	TOTAL HARVEST (PIECES)	TOTAL BIOMASS (kg)	SUR(%)	Pro/Lac	TOTAL FEED	FCR
1	0.49	1,45,000	19-Apr-23	13-Aug-23	116	1580	32	50560	8-Sep-23	142	2961	24.86	73610	124170	4541	85.63	3132	6184	1.36
2	0.49	1,45,000	19-Apr-23	4-Aug-23	107	969	38	36822	8-Sep-23	142	2851	28.95	82536	119358	3820	82.32	2634	5742	1.50
3	0.49	1,45,000	19-Apr-23	4-Aug-23	107	1285	36	46260	9-Sep-23	143	2014	32	64448	110708	3299	76.35	2275	5756	1.74
4	0.49	1,45,000	19-Apr-23	4-Aug-23	107	1436	43	61748	17-Sep-23	151	1952	31.5	61488	123236	3388	84.99	2337	4495	1.33
5	0.49	1,45,000	19-Apr-23	4-Aug-23	107	1433	34	48722	18-Sep-23	152	2059	28	57652	106374	3492	73.36	2408	5497	1.57
6	0.49	1,45,000	19-Apr-23	5-Aug-23	108	1340	41	54940	18-Sep-23	152	1769	34	60146	115086	3109	79.37	2144	5075	1.63
7	0.49	1,45,000	19-Apr-23	6-Aug-23	109	1211	39	47229	24-Sep-23	158	2575	28	72100	119329	3786	82.30	2611	6300	1.66
8	0.49	1,45,000	19-Apr-23	6-Aug-23	109	1315	36	47340	24-Sep-23	158	2532	25	63300	110640	3847	76.30	2653	5745	1.49
9	0.49	1,45,000	19-Apr-23	08-Aug-23	111	919	36	33084	25-Sep-23	159	2306	29	66874	99958	3225	68.94	2224	6291	1.95
10	1.06	3,00,000	19-Apr-23	5-Aug-23	108	2111	57	120327	26-Sep-23	160	3339	43	143577	263904	5450	87.97	1817	8915	1.64
11	0.91	2,59,000	19-Apr-23	5-Aug-23	108	1659	46	76314	27-Sep-23	161	2700	35	94500	170814	4359	65.95	1683	8046	1.85
12	0.95	2,16,000	19-Apr-23	6-Aug-23	109	1289	39	50271	27-Sep-23	161	3313	29	96077	146348	4602	67.75	2131	7260	1.58
13	0.67	1,94,000	19-Apr-23	6-Aug-23	109	1107	39	43173	25-Sep-23	159	3350	33	110550	153723	4457	79.24	2297	7623	1.71
14	0.63	1,72,000	19-Apr-23	8-Aug-23	111	1306	36	47016	24-Sep-23	158	3190	29	92510	139526	4496	81.12	2614	7223	1.61
15	0.56	1,51,000	19-Apr-23	8-Aug-23	111	1077	36	38772	17-Sep-23	151	3288	26	85488	124260	4365	82.29	2891	6713	1.54
16	0.73	2,16,000	19-Apr-23	8-Aug-23	111	1525	38	57950	9-Sep-23	143	4578	29	132762	190712	6103	88.29	2825	8648	1.42
TOTAL	9.92	28,13,000	-	-	109	21,562	39	8,60,528	-	153	44,777	30.33	13,57,619	22,18,147	66,339	78.85	2358	1,05,513	1.59

